

SOME ASPECTS OF ENSURING ROAD TRAFFIC SAFETY

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Abstract: This article analyzes several important aspects of ensuring road traffic safety. It examines the main causes of road traffic accidents, their consequences, and preventive measures. Special attention is also given to forming a safety culture among drivers and pedestrians, improving legislation, and applying modern information and technical tools (intelligent transport systems, video surveillance, digital platforms). The article develops practical methods and proposals for improving road traffic safety in the context of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: road traffic safety, road traffic accidents, prevention, safety culture, intelligent transport systems, drivers, pedestrians, legislation, monitoring

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" dated September 16, 2016, one of the main areas of activity for internal affairs bodies is ensuring road traffic safety. Their main tasks include: keeping records and registering vehicles, traffic rule violations, and road traffic accidents; processing documents related to road traffic accidents; removing a person from driving a vehicle and ensuring their examination in the prescribed manner to determine the state of intoxication, if there are grounds to believe they are intoxicated; prohibiting the use of vehicles whose technical condition does not meet established safety requirements; restricting or prohibiting repair, construction, and other work on streets and roads if road traffic safety requirements are not being met; and prohibiting the use of roads and railway crossings that do not comply with road traffic safety standards, rules, and norms[1].

Also, Article 10 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Road Traffic" [2] defines the following tasks of the State Road Safety Service:

- participates in the development and implementation of state programs in the field of road traffic;
- develops draft regulatory legal acts and normative documents in the field of road traffic within its competence;
- exercises state control over compliance with road traffic legislation within its competence;
- participates in determining the routes of heavy, oversized, dangerous, and special cargo transport vehicles;
- reviews and coordinates projects for the construction, reconstruction, and major repair of roads, railway crossings, as well as gas stations and other structures located along roads and in roadside areas, regarding traffic management;
- participates in the work of commissions for the acceptance into operation of road facilities and railway crossings where construction (reconstruction) and major repairs have been completed;

- exercises control over the technical condition of vehicles in operation and conducts mandatory technical inspections of vehicles (with the exception of category M1 vehicles belonging to individuals);

- organizes and carries out road traffic monitoring;

- exercises control over the technical condition of technical means of traffic management, as well as the preservation of roads and railway crossings, and their equipment with traffic regulation means;

- prohibits, in accordance with the established procedure, the use of roads and railway crossings that do not meet the requirements of regulatory documents in the field of road traffic;

- carries out road traffic management activities;

- issues instructions to road owners on the installation or removal of technical means of traffic management, and monitors the timelines and quality of their execution;

- restricts or prohibits the movement of vehicles on the road (on a road section) in accordance with Article 23 of the Law "On Road Traffic";

- implements information and communication technologies in the field of road traffic;

- considers proposals for the implementation of works on roads and roadside areas, coordinated with the relevant organizations;

- within its powers, submits mandatory representations to state bodies or other organizations and their officials to eliminate deficiencies in the installation and operation of technical means of road traffic management, or to rectify deficiencies in the event of a situation on any road section that threatens traffic safety or allows for a violation of Traffic Rules; in the event of failure to take measures to implement these written representations, applies administrative penalties;

- organizes the design, installation (assembly), replacement, and removal of technical means of traffic management, and monitors the execution of these works;

- carries out the installation (assembly), replacement, removal, and maintenance of technical means for traffic management on the streets of the cities of Tashkent and Nukus, as well as regional and district (city) centers;

- Maintains the location of technical means for organizing road traffic on the streets of the cities of Tashkent and Nukus, as well as regional and district (city) centers, and exercises state control over their compliance with location and technical condition;

- maintains records of vehicles, traffic violations, and road traffic accidents, and carries out their registration;

- issues national driver's licenses, motor vehicle registration certificates, and state registration license plates for motor vehicles and their trailers (semi-trailers);

- considers cases of administrative offenses within its competence [3].

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 4, 2022, No. PP-190 "On measures to reliably ensure human safety and drastically reduce mortality on highways," in order to guarantee the protection of human life and health from any accidents on highways in the conditions of New Uzbekistan, the following have been identified as urgent directions for ensuring road safety in our country:

- improving road infrastructure and improving its quality, creating reliable conditions for the safe movement of road users based on the priority of "pedestrian - public transport - bicycle transport - motor transport";

bringing the educational process to a qualitatively new level by introducing innovative pedagogical technologies into the system of training, retraining, and advanced training of drivers;

increasing the culture of compliance with traffic rules among drivers and pedestrians, ensuring the inevitability of punishment for any violation;

introduction of the basics of traffic rules from childhood, introduction of this practice in preschool educational organizations and general education schools;

full digitalization of traffic management, introduction of new management and control systems with the introduction of advanced information and communication technologies[4].

In recent years, the need to regulate the road safety service system in the country has become one of the primary directions of state policy. Therefore, at the initiative of the head of state, important measures were taken to stabilize the security system and ensure peace and tranquility in the republic.

Territorial internal affairs bodies perform the following functions in the field of road safety services:

- obtaining, summarizing, analyzing, and evaluating information from lower levels related to ensuring road safety, determining and implementing measures to ensure road safety, taking into account the dynamics of road infrastructure and traffic accidents, traffic violations, road congestion levels, and the technical condition of vehicles;

- organizing preventive measures to ensure road safety and prevent road traffic accidents, summarizing, analyzing their results, and developing measures to increase their effectiveness;

- ensuring traffic safety and providing assistance to road users, protecting their life, health, and property, and protecting their legal rights and interests;

- monitoring the condition of highways, streets, artificial structures on them, and railway crossings, ensuring they are equipped with traffic control systems, and complying with traffic safety requirements during construction and repair works;

- exercising technical supervision over the technical condition of motor vehicles and ensuring compliance with safety and legislative requirements during their operation, and organizing mandatory technical inspections of motor vehicles;

- organizing and monitoring the implementation of measures by ministries, departments, and organizations to improve the technical condition of vehicles, strengthen driver discipline, and increase the efficiency of traffic safety services;

- implementation of measures to protect the environment from the harmful effects of motor vehicles and monitoring the implementation of legislative acts;

- state registration, re-registration, and deregistration of motor vehicles and their trailers, issuance of vehicle registration certificates and state license plates, taking exams on traffic rules, and issuing vehicle driving licenses based on the results;

- identifying administrative offenses committed in the transport and communications system, conducting, formalizing, and reviewing pre-investigation checks on them;

- promotion of traffic rules, coverage in the mass media of measures implemented to prevent road accidents and ensure traffic safety, as well as conducting events aimed at increasing the legal culture of citizens on traffic safety issues.

The nature of the tasks and functions performed by the units of the State Road Safety Service determines their organizational structure. This structure is the system of apparatus and

units of the State Road Safety Service, based on the subordination of lower levels to higher ones and having a certain relationship, as well as the internal structure of individual apparatus and units, which is a list of the positions of its employees. Except for tasks and functions in the organizational structure. Factors such as the national-state and administrative-territorial division of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the number and socio-demographic composition of the population living in a specific territory, economic development, and the level of crime influence the state of road safety.

The apparatus of the state road safety service at the first and second levels primarily carries out organizational activities, focusing on providing daily organizational and methodological guidance to the apparatus and units of local subordinate services. They perform the functions of ensuring road safety and maintaining public order in the event of complicated operational situations (emergencies, natural disasters, etc.). These apparatuses lead the units of the road safety service under their operational jurisdiction—the paramilitary units of the road patrol service and other services and units—and primarily perform management functions.

The third link of the system, road safety departments (units, groups) of district (city) administrations (departments), performs the following functions in the field of ensuring road safety:

- formalizing and studying road traffic accidents and traffic violations in assigned territories, taking measures to improve the technical condition of vehicles and road transport infrastructure, as well as the level of road congestion, preparing relevant information and proposals based on the analysis and submitting them to the leading internal affairs bodies;
- submitting proposals to local khokimiyats on road traffic management and eliminating congestion in city and district areas, ensuring even distribution of vehicle traffic on streets, and improving road conditions;
- conducting a critical analysis of road traffic accidents committed in the territory, including cases of material damage, and conducting organizational and practical measures in cooperation with military units and other internal affairs services to prevent road traffic accidents;
- identifying locations with a high frequency of road traffic accidents on roads based on critical analysis, taking measures to eliminate them in cooperation with relevant road utilities, and taking them into account when organizing the activities of formation units within the service area;
- conducting investigations into road traffic accidents related to traffic safety violations and administrative offenses during the operation of vehicles, carrying out work to prevent road traffic accidents and traffic violations, as well as combating them, identifying persons involved in the commission of offenses, organizing on the basis of an analysis of the service activities of the personnel of enlisted units within the service area, and submitting proposals to enlisted units in this regard;
- in cooperation with other internal affairs services, searching for kidnapped, stolen vehicles and drivers hiding from the scene of a traffic accident, and carrying out work to solve crimes related to vehicles within a short timeframe;
- accelerating search operations to locate vehicles in motion in order to identify vehicles handed over for detention by various law enforcement agencies;

- Consideration of administrative offense cases in accordance with the procedure established by law, as well as submission of representations to officials regarding the elimination of the causes and conditions for committing offenses;
- conducting technical inspections of motor vehicles and special and seasonal inspections of roads and railway crossings;
- implementing preventive measures aimed at improving the technical condition of vehicles at enterprises, departments, associations, and organizations, strengthening driver discipline, and monitoring the implementation of measures to increase the efficiency of traffic safety services within them;
- cooperation with other internal affairs systems, state bodies, and civil society institutions in ensuring road safety, and the exchange of information and data with them;
- conducting discussions and meetings at enterprises, departments, organizations, mahallas, educational, and other institutions, and conducting open dialogues with the population to enhance the legal culture of citizens on traffic safety issues;
- organizing preventive and advocacy work aimed at preventing traffic violations by drivers, pedestrians, and especially minor children, involving public representatives, and covering ongoing activities in the mass media.

References:

- [1] Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" dated September 16, 2016 // <https://lex.uz>.
- [2] Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Road Traffic" dated January 19, 2024 // <https://lex.uz>.
- [3] Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Road Traffic" dated January 19, 2024 // <https://lex.uz>.
- [4] Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-190 dated April 4, 2022, "On measures to reliably ensure human safety and drastically reduce mortality on highways" // <https://lex.uz>.

